

Supplementary tables

Table S1. Statistics describing the difference between “true” and estimated proportions of origination and extinction across all spatial bins (n = 60000) produced in the simulations (see Figure 3a).

	Raw origination	Raw extinction	BC origination	BC extinction	3T origination	3T extinction
Median	0.144	0.202	0.139	0.195	0.012	-0.011
Inter-quartile range	0.181	0.118	0.190	0.120	0.154	0.078

Table S2. Occurrence counts across space, time, and clades for Permian marine invertebrate data. Paleolatitude bins are labelled with their midpoint.

Palaeo-latitude	Clade	Roadian	Wordian	Capitanian	Wuchiapingian	Changhsingian
75	Brachiopoda	30	71	50	2	16
45	Brachiopoda	383	434	238	417	161
15	Brachiopoda	3636	2197	1872	3000	3796
-15	Brachiopoda	314	946	651	1007	362
-45	Brachiopoda	556	972	394	4858	1071
-75	Brachiopoda	318	387	34	686	111
75	Bivalvia	82	95	85	52	42
45	Bivalvia	77	24	12	134	6
15	Bivalvia	538	294	226	1231	736
-15	Bivalvia	16	91	21	61	35
-45	Bivalvia	56	44	39	183	143
-75	Bivalvia	80	139	52	311	19
75	Cephalopoda	18	0	0	0	3
45	Cephalopoda	36	34	4	36	47
15	Cephalopoda	210	135	55	237	820
-15	Cephalopoda	32	149	44	210	430
-45	Cephalopoda	64	15	2	39	9
-75	Cephalopoda	1	0	0	3	0
75	Gastropoda	1	1	2	4	1
45	Gastropoda	0	0	2	23	6
15	Gastropoda	800	117	147	337	234
-15	Gastropoda	36	126	131	67	3
-45	Gastropoda	12	34	22	196	218
-75	Gastropoda	13	43	20	49	15

Table S3. Occurrence counts across space, time, and clades for Triassic marine invertebrate data. Paleolatitude bins are labelled with their midpoint.

Palaeolatitude	Clade	Induan	Olenekian	Anisian	Ladinian
75	Brachiopoda	2	6	32	21
45	Brachiopoda	35	66	174	13
15	Brachiopoda	445	171	1292	190
-15	Brachiopoda	0	2	61	8
-45	Brachiopoda	13	1	68	4
-75	Brachiopoda	0	0	110	369
75	Bivalvia	43	111	218	126
45	Bivalvia	449	326	182	159
15	Bivalvia	1997	1558	1799	969
-15	Bivalvia	106	25	68	15
-45	Bivalvia	56	35	17	7
-75	Bivalvia	0	0	37	35
75	Cephalopoda	136	454	331	113
45	Cephalopoda	625	1080	280	222
15	Cephalopoda	427	2315	4086	742
-15	Cephalopoda	30	350	224	25
-45	Cephalopoda	513	647	178	9
-75	Cephalopoda	0	1	13	2
75	Gastropoda	3	1	2	1
45	Gastropoda	76	8	53	26
15	Gastropoda	195	306	645	395
-15	Gastropoda	25	2	1	9
-45	Gastropoda	17	16	13	0
-75	Gastropoda	0	0	9	6